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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF E-CONTENT ON HISTORY SUBJECT (THE BEGINNING OF MODERN AGE) OF IX STANDARD STUDENTS

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Abstract

Technology in the information revolution has provided many unique benefits to instructional programs. Normally in the growth of technology applications in education, we are moving towards a Virtual Reality where the distance between the teacher and the taught is nil. The possibility of such virtual reality can be made by generating good e-Contents and accessible by all. E-contents are basically a package that satisfies the conditions like i.e. minimization of the distance, cost effectiveness, user-friendliness and adaptability to local conditions. The purpose of this study is to develop and validate e-content package on the unit “the Beginning of Modern Age” of IX standard student’s history syllabus of Tamil Nadu government.

Keywords: Development; Validation; E-Content; History.

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1. Introduction

In the field of education there is no restriction on students to learn the basic concepts of reading and writing. The modern age gives more chances to the students to face the world with all that they have learned at school level. The new and modern education system involves modern information and communication technologies in the teaching-learning process for teaching the 21st Century students. Technology is a powerful tool for problem-solving, conceptual development and critical thinking. ‘E-content’ is one of the recent techniques in the educational technology. In this e-content way of instruction teaching is learner centric. The expansion for e-content is electronic content. E-content is a product of e-learning. The products bring solutions to facilitate quick and efficient development in education. To maintain standard or quality in education one should make use of e-content in the teaching-learning process.

2. Development and Validation of E-Content Package

The objective of the present study is to develop and validate an e-content package on the unit the Beginning of Modern Age. In order to prepare and validate the e-content package the investigator followed a number of steps, which are given under the following headings.

3. Identification of History Unit

In order to develop an e-content package, the investigator selected unit “the Beginning of Modern Age” in the syllabus of IX standard history subject after consultation with history lecturers and post graduate history teachers working in higher secondary schools.

4. Identification of Teaching Points

The investigator identified the teaching points for the unit the Beginning of Modern Age in the IX standard history subject of Tamil Nadu State Board syllabus following English Medium.

5. Review By Experts

The investigator presented the teaching points to the history lecturers and post graduate history teachers working in higher secondary schools and they were appraised about the purpose of the experiment. After this, the history teachers verified and reviewed the teaching points. This ensures content validity and face validity of the items.

Table 1: Development of E-Content Package

CONTENT	E-CONTENT
Introduction	Audio/ Video/Images
The Age of Reason	Audio/ Video/Images
Renaissance	Audio/ Video/Images
Renaissance in Italy	Audio/ Video
The Renaissance Movement	Audio/ Video
Art	Audio/ Video/Images
Sculpture and Paintings	Audio/ Video/Images
Music	Audio/ Video/Images
Rise of Humanism	Audio/ Video
Humanism	Audio/ Video
Science	Audio/ Video/Images
Printing and Mariner's Compass	Audio/ Video/Images
Results of the Renaissance	Audio/ Video
Reformation	Audio/ Video/Images
Martin Luther	Audio/ Video/Images
Imperial Diet	Audio/ Images
Protestants	Audio/ Images
Counter Reformation	Audio/ Images
Ignatius Loyola and the Society of Jesus	Audio/ Video/Images
The Council of Trent	Audio/ Images

The Inquisition and Index	Audio/ Images
Geographical Discoveries (Knowledge about Earth)	Audio
Prince Henry	Audio/ Video/Images
The Fall of Constantinople	Audio/ Video
Marco Polo	Audio/ Video/Images
Bartholomeo Diaz	Audio/ Video/Images
Vasco das Gama	Audio/ Video/Images
Christopher Columbus	Audio/ Video/Images
Fernando Cortez	Audio/ Video/Images
Ferdinand Magellan	Audio/ Video/Images
Amerigo Vespucci & Martin Wald Muller	Audio/ Video/Images

6. Development of Script for E-Content Package

After consultation with experts, the investigator prepared the script for the e-content package. The script was prepared not missing even a single teaching point for the study of unit “the Beginning of Modern Age”. Based on the script, the investigator developed the e-content package for the subject unit. The developed script was given to history teachers to check the accuracy of content of the script.

The following steps were used to develop the scripts

- Knowing the subject: Gathered all the materials, met people, went to libraries read newspaper, reviews on relevant documents were done. Materials were collected widely.
- Arranging the sentence packets as logically as possible going from familiar to unfamiliar ending with appropriate conclusions.
- Rewriting and necessary finishing was done to give the final product unity, proportion and continuity.
- The drafting of the full length scripts with a complete list of visual illustrations and accompanying sound, voice and music.

The shooting script was made by breaking down the screen play into shots by the investigator and taking care of the details of the technical aspects. The shooting script was the blue print of the whole e-content. It gave the complete picture of the final schedule. It had all the details of camera dimension, lighting suggestion, music and sound. This is how the script was transferred into e-content form.

7. Developing Visual Content

After the scripts were written, the contents of the selected topics were transferred into the form of visuals. Visuals were made to use for illustrative talk, When Audio instruction presented with the use of visuals, it clarifies the concept and leads to the meaningful association of ideas. As far as the visual components were concerned, visuals were made. Rough drafts of simple and uncluttered layouts were prepared. Then these sketches were given to the artist. Then e-content with logical sequence were shot from the visual.

Table 2: Schematic Presentation of Development of E-Content Package

For the development of e-content package	Purpose
History lecturers and post graduate history teachers working in higher secondary schools	For getting ideas regarding construction of e-content package and identifying teaching points of the Beginning of Modern Age.
Four IX standard students from Vivekananda Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Uthukottai, Tiruvallur District, TamilNadu.	For trying out the e-content package
Two Experts	For validating e-content package

8. Try Out of E-Content Package

The prepared e-content package was played back to four IX standard students from Vivekananda Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Uthukottai, Tiruvallur District, TamilNadu. The e-content package ran for 2 hours 47 minutes.

9. Validation of E-Content Package

In order to validate the e-content package, the investigator gave the e-content package to two experts. Then two experts gave their feedback. Based on their feedback modifications were done in the package. The modified e-content package was again reviewed by the experts. This approved the final form of the e-content package.

10. Conclusion

In this present study the investigator has developed and validated e-content package on the unit “the Beginning of Modern Age” in the IX standard history subject of Tamil Nadu State Board syllabus following English Medium.

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